

Self-Assessment System and Tax Compliance in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study conceptually examined the effect of self-assessment system on tax compliance in Nigeria using extensive review of existing literatures. Procedural Justice Theory was adopted to guide the present study this is because the theory postulate that the existence of fairness in procedures may lead to fairness in outcome. Based on the review of the existing literatures, previous findings revealed that self-assessment system improves tax compliance in Nigeria. The study concluded that on average, tax education and fairness as measures of self-assessment have impacted on tax compliance in Nigeria positively and significantly. The study recommended that government should ensure tax payers education and fairness in the Nigerian tax systems so that the compliance will be improved.

Keywords: Self-assessment, Tax compliance, Fairness, Tax payers.

How to Cite:

INTRODUCTION

Tax non-compliance is the unwillingness of a tax payer to remit the proper amount or fail to comply with the relevant tax laws. Tax Compliance is the process in which tax returns required to be submitted to the tax authorities are filed at the appropriate time with the accurate tax liability as required under the tax laws and regulations of a country (Friedman, 2011). Tax compliance could be capitulative compliance, committed compliance and creative compliance. Capitulative compliance occurs when taxpayers unwillingly fulfil their obligation, but they still

fulfil; inversely, committed compliance refers to a situation where taxpayers voluntarily pay taxes without complains or public coercion; creative compliance, on the other hand, describes a situation when taxpayers take an action to reduce tax liability by re-examining income and expenses within legal context,McBarnett’s model (as cited in Alabede, zaima&khamil, 2011). Compliance with taxation is a condition in which the taxpayer fulfills and implements all dues in the Tax Assessment System (Devano&Kurnia, 2011;in Asrinanda, 2018).Tax assessment system is of two types. The Official Assessment System (OAS) and Self-Assessment System (SAS). Official Assessment System is also known as administrative assessment. Under this method,the taxpayers file their returns and report their assessable incomes to the tax authority. The tax administration examines taxpayer’s returns and financial statements, calculate the amount of tax payable, and notify the taxpayers of the tax liability. However, administrative assessment systems are said to have been resource-intensive and tend to be ineffective, costly, inefficient and complex to administer since it imposes much burden on tax administrators. As a result of its drawbacks and challenges various countries abandoned the administrative assessment system and sought for another alternative system of Self-assessment.

The self-assessment tax regime is a system of tax administration whereby the tax payer is granted the right, by law, to compute his own tax liability, pays the tax due (at the designated bank) and produces evidence of tax paid at the time of filing his tax return at the tax office, on due date. Self-assessment applies to employees, self-employed, limited liability companies including oil and gas companies; agents/taxable persons, in the case of value added tax (VAT). The main feature of the self-assessment system is the self-finishing of tax returns and tax payments from various levels of background so that simplification of tax returns and administration can potentially help Taxpayers to resolve their tax returns accurately and

improve compliance (Palil&Mustapa, 2011). In the self assessment system Taxpayer is given the widest possible freedom in calculating the amount of tax payable that becomes obligation. Ideally, if this function is effective, then the amount of tax payable, reported by the Taxpayer in his SPT should be known to be true Hutagaol (2016).

Before the inception of Buhari administration, oil used to be the major source of Nigerian revenue. However, following the fall in oil prices in an international market, governments have simply tried to increase the level of tax compliance by adopting an intransigent attitude towards all taxpayers and by applying laws and regulations to sanction and fine evaders. These means of enforcement proved to be without a significant success. Towards the end of the 20th century, governments have realized that a change is needed in order to increase the amount of taxes collected (Batrancea, Nichita and Batrancea (2012). Mukura and Phiri, (2020) says there is an increasing need for the governments to collect more revenue by way of taxes to face its enormous financial obligations and meet budgeted expenditures.

The current administration of President Muhammad Buhari (PMB) aims at paying considerable attention on other multiple sources of revenue, such as corporate income tax as spelt out in the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan for 2017-2020 (ERGP, 2017).

Administration of income tax in Nigeria as in some other developing countries is characterized by low compliance level and despite Nigeria human and natural endowment as well as economic potentiality, the country has continued to record one of the lowest tax compliance level in Africa (CITN 2010). There is a growing emphasis on the need for tax authorities, especially in developing economies, to develop a new perspective on how to increase the tax revenue of their economies. This study therefore conceptually assesses Self-assessment system and tax compliance in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Tax Compliance

Tax Compliance (TC) has attracted much discussion in the tax literature. According to Jackson (1986), is reporting of tax liability to the relevant authority in compliance with applicable tax laws, regulation and court. Tax compliance is an obligation that is fulfilled by taxpayers based on the taxpayers' perception of the fairness of the tax burden they bear, and the effect of satisfaction on government services (Husin, Husina, Wahyuniati & Nofian, 2021). Tax compliance is defined as the willingness of a taxpayer to conform to the laws by voluntarily declaring his income accurately and filing his tax return and paying the tax due at the appropriate date (Etim, Umoffong & Bassey, 2020). Alternatively, tax compliance may mean an outright failure to settle taxes as and when due.

Determinants of Tax Compliance

According to Deyganto (2011), determinant of tax compliance include but not limited to the following:

Economic Factors

It includes sub-factors like tax rate, income level and perception on government spending

Social Factors

Tax influencing factors from the social perspective refer to willingness of taxpayers to comply with tax laws based on norms and value of their society. It comprises: perception on equity and fairness, change in government policy and peer group influence.

Institutional Factors

It refers to the relationship that exists between government/tax authorities and taxpayers regarding tax collection and payment procedure. The institutional factors contain sub-factors like efficiency of tax authority, probability of being audited, and simplicity of the tax system According to Okon and Israel (2020), The determinant of tax compliance are:

Personal financial constraint (PFINCON), Awareness of offences and penalties (AWAOP), Tax rate (TAXRAT), Ethics and attitude of taxpayers (ETHATTD), Perception of equity and fairness (EQIFAR), Income level (INCOM), and Level of education (EDU) are speculated by the researchers as factors influencing the level of tax compliance.

Concept of Self-assessment

Asrinanda (2018) Self assessment system is a tax collection system adopted in Indonesia today. Self assessment system is a taxation system that gives trust to Taxpayers to fulfill and implement their own obligations and tax rights.

Hutauruk (2019), Self-Assessment System According to this taxation system, the amount of tax owed determine by the taxpayer. In this case, the activity of calculating, depositing, and reporting the tax due is carried out by the taxpayer. Borongo, (2020), Self-assessment system Refers to self-determination of tax liability by an individual or company where they are required to file their return, calculate taxable income, calculate amount of tax and pay their tax on due dates and provide evidence of the tax paid at the time of filling tax return at the tax office. In this system a taxpayer is believed to be faithful on presenting their income for taxation and tax authority is left with control and providing reliable information to taxpayers relating to tax issues.

Prerequisites/conditions Necessary of SAS

- i. Level of honesty and integrity to taxpayer
- ii. Record keeping system
- iii. Education on importance of paying tax
- iv. Enablement by tax authorities for example; tax forms, instructions on those tax forms etc.
- v. Sanctions for failure to comply for example; tax penalties

Advantages of using Self-Assessment system

- i. Reduces administrative costs by tax authorities where they just select few taxpayers for audit
- ii. Minimizes the possibility of tax disputes
- iii. Reduces corruption by reducing contact with taxpayer
- iv. It promotes tax compliance and good citizenship

Disadvantages of using Self-Assessment system

- i. High compliance costs as same taxpayer need to use tax consultants
- ii. Dishonest trader may cheat on their true income and hence loss of government revenue.

Nigerian Self-Assessment system

In Nigeria, Self-Assessment System was introduced into tax administrative system with operational effect in 1992 and initially restricted to a threshold of taxpayers and extended to the rest in 1998. However, it was not until 2011 that its implementation became effective, through a project-based system. In a Self-Assessment System, a tax payer is required to assess and accurately calculate his tax liability using a tax return form in which he declares his gross income, allowable deductions, among others. The tax return must then be filed with the relevant tax authority together with a payment for the tax liability computed on the said return. Under Self- Assessment System, the tax authorities responsibilities, partially on assessing the tax return and determining the liabilities are been shifted to the taxpayer duly to declare all the necessary particulars pertaining to their income and expenses for that particular year of

assessment and submit the necessary returns together with all required supporting documents to the tax administrators (Etim, 2020).

SELF-ASSESSMENT AND TAX COMPLIANCE

FOREIGN STUDIES ON SELF-ASSESSMENT AND TAX COMPLIANCE

Barongo (2020) determines what influences taxpayers to comply with tax laws and regulations through Self-Assessment System in Tanzania. Tax compliance was used as dependent variable, and reporting requirements, filling condition, mode of payment as independent variables. Questionnaire was used in collecting the data. Descriptive analysis, factor analysis and regression analysis was used in analyzing the data. Findings showed that reporting requirements, filling condition & mode of payment influence tax compliance significantly influenced tax compliance. The study was conducted abroad and same need to be carrying out in Nigeria. Also tax knowledge as one of the major determinant in self-assessment is missing. Prasetyarini, Rusmana & Putri (2019) investigates the influence of tax payer's knowledge and penalties to the effectiveness of Tax Self-assessment System in Indonesia the variables used the study are self-assessment system as dependent variable and knowledge and penalty as independent variables. Multiple regression method of data analysis was used. Findings of this study showed that knowledge and penalties have positive influence on Self-Assessment System. The study was conducted abroad and same need to be carrying out in Nigeria. The use of penalty is not recommended since the aim is to encourage voluntary compliance.

Hutauruk, Ghozali, Sutarmo, Mushofa, Suyanto and Yulidar (2019) analyze the effect of the self-assessment system and tax control and tax control as a mediator on tax payments in Indonesia. The variables used are self-assessment system as independent variable and Tax

revenue as dependent. The data was collected using primary method through questionnaire media with semantic differential scale seven ranges. SEM PLS approach was used in analysing the data. Findings of this study showed that Self-Assessment System has a significant effect on the payment of tax. The study was conducted abroad and same need to be carrying out in Nigeria.

Asrinanda (2018) examined the influence of tax knowledge, self-assessment system and tax awareness on taxpayer compliance in Banda Aceh City, Indonesia. the variables used are Tax compliance as dependent variable and Tax knowledge and Tax Awareness as independent. The data was collected using primary method through questionnaire media. Multiple linear regression method of data analysis was used. Findings of this study showed that Tax knowledge, self assessment system and tax awareness have significant and positive impact on tax compliance. The study was conducted abroad and same need to be carry out in Nigeria.

Terrefe (2016) explores the implementation of self-assessment tax system and its impact on the tax compliance in Ethiopia. The variables used are Tax compliance as dependent variable and self-assessment system as independent variable. The data was collected using primary method through questionnaire and was analysed using simple percentage. Findings of this study showed that self-assessment system have not significantly and positively impacted on tax compliance. The study was conducted abroad and same need to be carry out in Nigeria. The method of analysis is too elementary.

Husina, Hamida and Bulana (2012) determines and analyzes the effect of taxpayer awareness, tax knowledge, tax sanctions, and public service accountability on taxpayer compliance in Indonesia. Tax compliance was used as dependent variable, and taxpayer awareness, tax knowledge, tax sanctions, and public service accountability as independent variables. Data was

collected using Questionnaire. Multiple linear regression method was used in analyzing the data. Findings established that taxpayer awareness, tax knowledge, tax sanctions, and public service accountability had positive and significant effects on tax compliance. The study was conducted abroad and same need to be carry out in Nigeria. There is need to revalidate the study as the time used was old.

NIGERIAN STUDIES ON SELF-ASSESSMENT AND TAX COMPLIANCE

Adekoya and Enyi (2020) investigates the probable influence of Control of corruption on individual taxpayers' voluntary tax compliance behavior in Nigeria. The variables used are Tax compliance as dependent variable, and Control of Corruption & Trust in Government as independent variables. Questionnaire was used in collecting the data. descriptive and inferential statistics was used in analyzing the data. Findings showed that Control of Corruption & Trust in Government have significant influence on tax compliance. The study used only some of the determinant of self-assessment leaving out many like tax knowledge, simplicity of the tax system and convenience.

Irefe-esema and Akinmade (2020) Automation and Tax Compliance in Nigeria. Tax compliance was used as dependent variable, and registration, filing & reporting and payment compliance as independent variables. Interview was used as method of data collection. Descriptive analysis was employed. Findings showed that Registration & payment improve while filing & reporting have not improve tax compliance. The method of data collection used (interview) is not verifiable

Agbetunde (2020) examined culture and tax compliance of individual taxpayers in Nigeria. Tax compliance was used as dependent variable, and culture as independent variables. data was collected using questionnaire. parametric and nonparametric statistics was used in analyzing

the data. Findings established cultural dimensions has significant influence on tax compliant. The study used only some of the determinant of self-assessment leaving out many like tax knowledge, simplicity of the tax system and convenience.

Nwidiuudu, Obuah, Wariboko&Barikiu (2020) ascertained the importance of taxpayers education and tax compliance in Nigeria. tax compliance was used as dependent variable, and Tax education as independent variables. Questionnaire was used in collecting the data. descriptive/survey method of data analysis was employed. Findings showed that Taxpayer' education have not significant impact on tax compliance in Nigeria. The study used only some of the determinant of self-assessment leaving out many like simplicity of the tax system and convenience.

Umoffon andetim (2020) evaluates the individual and socio-economic factors as tax compliance determinants in Self-Assessment System (SAS) of tax administration in Nigeria. Tax compliance was used as dependent variable, and Individual and socio-economic factor, Awareness of offences & penalties and tax rates as independent variables. Questionnaire was used in collecting the data. Description and regression analyses method was used. Findings showed that Individual and socio-economic factor, awareness of offences & penalties has positive and significant impact while tax rates has a negative impact on tax compliance. The study used only some of the determinant of self-assessment leaving out many like tax knowledge, simplicity of the tax system and convenience.

Etim, Jeremiah and Dan (2020) examined the effect of digitalization of economy on tax compliance in Nigeria, Tax compliance was used as dependent variable, and Digitalization of economy, as independent variables. Questionnaire was used in collecting the data. Simple percentage, descriptive statistics, and linear regression techniques was used in analyzing the

data.. Findings showed that Digitalization has negative influence on tax compliance. The method of analysis used is too elementary.

Okon and Israel (2020) evaluates and understand tax compliance determinants in Nigeria. Variables used are tax rate, level of income, perception on government spending, government policy, simplicity of tax system and efficiency of the tax authority, perception on equity and peer influence. The data was collected using questionnaire. Multinomial regression was employed in analysis. Findings of this study showed that tax rate, level of income, perception on government spending, government policy, simplicity of tax system and efficiency of the tax authority have significant impact. perception on equity and peer influence have insignificant impact. The study used only some of the determinant of self-assessment leaving out many like tax knowledge, simplicity of the tax system and convenience.

Oluwafadekemi, Obindah and Evans (2020) assessed tax compliance among small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria. The variables used are; Public goods and services, trust in govt, taxpayer's knowledge, perception & penalty as independent variables and tax compliance as dependent variable. The data was collected using secondary method. Generalised ordered logistic regression analysis was employed. Findings showed that knowledge, tax penalty, and trust in the government have significant and positive relationship with Tax compliance. Use of penalty is not recommended.

Eluro (2018) examines the determinants of tax compliance under the self-assessment scheme in private secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial zone in Nigeria. Variables used are Tax clearance and Social acceptance as independent variable and Tax compliance as dependent. The data was collected using questionnaire media with semantic differential scale seven ranges. Descriptive, Inferential stat & T-test was used in analysing the data. Findings of this study

showed that Compliance is mostly determined by tax clearance and social acceptance. Causes of non-compliance are:-Complexity of filing process is the highest, -no much incentives from govt, -tax control significantly influence the tax payment, - tax control is also able to moderate the SAS against the tax payment. The study used only some of the determinant of self-assessment leaving out many like tax knowledge, simplicity of the tax system and convenience.

Yahaya,Abba andSulaiman (2018) explores relationship between corporate taxpayers' knowledge on SAS and compliance behavior in Nigeria. Tax compliance was used as dependent variable, and tax awareness usedas independent variables.Data was collected using questionnaire. Multiple regression modelswere used in analyzing the data. Findings establishedthere is a positive relationship between awareness on Self-Assessment System and compliance behavior. The study used only some of the determinant of self-assessment leaving out many like simplicity of the tax system and convenience.

Olaoye, Abiodun andAbiola (2017) examined the impact of tax information, administration and knowledge on tax payers' compliance in Nigeria.Tax compliance was used as dependent variable, and tax information, administration and knowledgeas independent variables. Data was collected using questionnaire. Ordinary least square regression method was used in analyzing the data Findings established Tax information and knowledge had positive significant while tax administration had an insignificant impact impacts on tax compliance. The study used only some of the determinant of self-assessment leaving out many like tax knowledge, simplicity of the tax system and convenience.

Oladipupu andobazee (2016) investigates the impact of tax payer's knowledge and penalties on tax compliance in Nigeria. The variables used are tax complianceas dependent variable and

tax payer's knowledge and penalties as independent variables. The data was collected using questionnaire. Ordinary least square regression method was used. Findings showed that Tax knowledge has significant impact, penalties have insignificant impact on tax compliance. The time the study was conducted was too old, there is need to reexamine the tax system in Nigeria as at 2021.

Theoretical Framework

This study is guided by the Procedural justice theory (PJT). The theory is developed by Thibaut & Walker in 1975. The theory postulates that existence of fairness in procedures may lead to fairness in outcomes (Mas'ud, 2017). Put differently, PJT highlights that the employment of fair procedures may translate to voluntary tax compliance. When taxpayers perceived that the procedure of payment is less complex and simple, they may think that there will be fair treatment in the tax system which in essence will persuade them to comply with the tax pay. This theory is found relevant and is therefore adopted as underpinning this study.

METHODOLOGY

The data for this study are collected from the previously existed literature. The conclusions are done based on the findings obtained from the study.

CONCLUSION

From the above studies, it can be concluded that self-assessment system improves compliance both abroad and in Nigeria. On average, the variables that improve compliance positively and significantly are both abroad and in Nigeria are: tax payer's knowledge, fairness. Penalty and tax payer's attitude have mixed findings.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the findings/conclusion above, it is recommended that government should ensure that the tax payers are adequately educated about the tax system and the tax system has to be fair to them (tax payers) so that the compliance will be improved without necessary supervision or application of penalty.

SUGGESTION FOR FURTHER STUDIES

Having seen that knowledge impacted positively and significantly both abroad and in Nigeria, study on Tax knowledge as a moderator for self-assessment and tax compliance need to be carry out in Nigeria so as to see the extent to which knowledge impacted on both dependent and independent variables.

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